

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

Petar Bulat

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FAKTORI KOJI UTIČU NA ELIMINACIJU, KLINIČKU SLIKU I ISHOD AKUTNE INTOKSIKACIJE BENZODIAZEPINIMA KOD PACIJENATA STARIJE ŽIVOTNE DOBI

CHALLENGERS AND MODERN
APPROACHES IN CLINICAL
TOXICOLOGY CHAIRS

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Benzodiazepini su najčešće korišćeni lekovi u slučaju akutnih samotrovanja. Cilj ovog rada je analiza faktora koji utiču na proces eliminacije benzodiazepina, težinu kliničke slike, razvoj komplikacija i ishod akutne intoksikacije kod osoba starije životne dobi. Sprovedena je klinička opservaciona kohortna studija. Ukupno je analizirano 95 bolesnika hospitalno lečenih u Klinici za toksikologiju Vojnomedicinske akademije. Podeljeni su u tri grupe u odnosu na životnu dob (18-40 godina, 41-65 godina, stariji od 65) i praćeni su u skladu sa kliničkom slikom i detektovanim toksičnim koncentracijama minimalno 48 sati. Najčešće su intoksikacije bromazepamom, a poređenjem srednjih koncentracija bromazepama na prijemu među različitim dobnim grupama, u grupi starijih od 65 godina one su bile više, bez statističke značajnosti u odnosu na mlađe dobne grupe. Eliminacija benzodiazepina je analizirana poređenjem koncentracija lekova na prijemu i određivanjem procentulanog smanjenja koncentracije posle 24 i 48 sati.

Dominantan klinički znak u akutnim intoksikacijama benzodiazepinima je poremećaj stanja svesti različitog stepena procenjivan pomoću Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS). Procena težine trovanja vršena je u skladu sa Skalom težine trovanja (engl. Poisoning Severity Score, PSS). Pokazano je da je kod osoba starije životne dobi u poređenju sa drugim starosnim grupama metabolički kapacitet manji, a renalna eliminacija sporija. Kod starijih od 65 godina uočena je i češća hipoalbuminemija što doprinosi dužem održavanju toksičnih koncentracija benzodiazepina. Kod bolesnika starijih od 65 godina zabeležena je teža klinička slika (dugotrajniji poremećaji svesti, češći kardiovaskularni poremećaji), duža hospitalizacija, veća potreba za primenom antidota, češće komplikacije (aspiraciona pneumonija i rabdomioliza), oporavak sporiji, a letalitet veći.

KLJUČNE REČI: intoksikacije; benzodiazepini; stare osobe.

FACTORS AFFECTING BENZODIAZEPINES ELIMINATION, CLINICAL FEATURES AND OUTCOME IN ELDERLY PEOPLE ACUTELY POISONED WITH BENZODIAZEPINES

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Benzodiazepines are the most frequent drugs used in cases of deliberate self-poisoning. Aim of this study was analyzing the factors affecting the elimination process of benzodiazepines, severity of clinical features, complications and acute poisoning outcome in elderly patients. Clinical observation cohort study was made including 95 patients hospitalized in the Department of Clinical Toxicology in Belgrade. Patients were divided into three groups according to their age (18-40; 41-65; ≥65 years old).

Patients were monitored in accordance with the clinical features as well as the detected toxic concentrations of benzodiazepines in 48-hour period. The most common ingested benzodiazepine was bromazepam. Comparing the mean concentration of bromazepam among different age groups, drug concentration is slightly higher in group of elderly people, but not statistically important compared to younger age groups. Drug elimination was analyzed by comparing its concentration after 24 and 48 hours. Dominant clinical characteristic of an acute benzodiazepine intoxication is different level of consciousness disorder estimated by Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS). Evaluation of the poisoning was performed in accordance with the Poisoning Severity Score (PSS). The study shows that metabolic capacity decreases and renal elimination is slower in elderly people compared to other age groups. More common hypoalbuminemia is also observed in group of elderly people, contributing to extended maintenance of toxic concentrations of benzodiazepines. Severe clinical features is observed in elderly population- deeper and prolonged disorders of consciousness, more common cardiovascular disorder, longer hospitalization, increased need for antidotes, frequent complications (aspiration bronchopneumonia and rhabdomyolysis), slower recovery and higher lethality.

KEYWORDS: self-poisoning; benzodiazepines; elderly